

IAM4NFDI

IAM4NFDI - Service Onboarding Handbook

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1 Introduction

As part of the NFDI, an authentication and authorization infrastructure (“NFDI-AAI”) has been established, which is harmoniously integrated into the research federation (“DFN-AAI”) operated by the DFN via corresponding standards. There are various options for providers of services in the context of data-driven research infrastructures to connect their services to this NFDI-AAI. This document serves as a source of information and a decision-making aid for these service providers.

The NFDI-AAI is a hierarchical system in which not only the user administrations of individual NFDI consortia or individual so-called Virtual Organizations (VO), each of which belongs to an NFDI consortium, are integrated, but also central components, in particular the identity provider proxy DFN eduID and an NFDI infrastructure proxy for generic NFDI services.

The first decision to be made for a service provider is based on the intended target group for the service: 1) should the service be available only to a single VO, 2) to an entire NFDI specialist consortium or 3) to all NFDI specialist consortia simultaneously.

If 1.) or 2.) is the case, the service should be connected to one of the subject-specific CAAs; if 3.) is the case, it should be integrated with the infra proxy.

The following text first discusses the general technical basics, such as the architecture, attributes, authorization, policies, incident response, federation and finally the various levels at which a service can be integrated, namely the individual CAAs and the infrastructure proxy.

The second main chapter then deals explicitly with the service connection itself, again subdivided into the connection to the infrastructure proxy and the four different CAAI solutions (AcademicID, didmos, RegApp and Unity) in the sense of a practical guide.

This document is only intended as an introduction to the topic; detailed technical instructions are maintained in the [project documentation](#).

2 Technical basics of the NFDI-AAI

2.1 Architecture and protocols

Figure 1: Architecture NFDI-AAI

The architecture of the NFDI CAAI essentially consists of the following two components:

- CAAs: Services that are to be available to individual specialist consortia or VOs are connected here. On the one hand, the consortia and communities can manage their members here. This saves having to do this process separately in each connected service. Secondly, the CAAs have a proxy component that can be used to translate between different protocols, in particular SAML and OpenID Connect/OAuth2 (see below).
- NFDI infrastructure proxy: Services that are aimed at several or all consortia are connected to this proxy, which reduces the technical requirements. It also makes it easier to manage people working in several consortia and to authorise the services.

More details and information about the connected components that are outside the IAM4NFDI project can be found here: <https://doc.nfdi-aai.de/architecture/>.

The SAML (Security Assertion Markup Language) and OIDC (OpenID Connect) protocols are used for secure and smooth integration with identity providers (IdP) and seamless authentication and authorization for applications.

SAML enables a secure single sign-on, a network across different applications and platforms as well as the exchange of user authentication and authorization information in a standardized way and ensures smooth communication between services and IdPs.

The OIDC protocol is an identity layer built on top of the OAuth 2.0 framework. It extends the OAuth 2.0 framework with an additional authentication protocol that allows third-party applications to verify the identity of end users and obtain basic user profile information. Information is exchanged between the client application and the OpenID Provider (OP) using JSON Web Tokens (JWTs).

2.2 Attributes

The mandatory and optional attributes and claims that the proxy component of a community AAI transmits to the connected services and, if applicable, to the infrastructure proxy are documented in the current version of the NFDI Infrastructure Attribute Policy (IAP), see <https://doc.nfdi-aai.de/policies/> and <https://doc.nfdi-aai.de/attributes/>.

Due to the current international activities (end of 2024), particularly in the [AARC community](#), it can be assumed that the attribute lists listed in the above-mentioned policy document will have to be adapted again with the adoption of guideline G056: AARC Profile for expressing identity attributes in order to remain internationally compatible.

In the context discussed here, those in Section 4 of the above-mentioned policy document, Community Attribute Profiles Attributes available from the Community AAIs, are relevant.

Services can generally expect the following user information to be transmitted by the CAAI:

- Name(s) of the person concerned
- e-mail address
- Identifier, generated by
 - the identity provider of the home institution
 - the edu-ID system
 - the community AAI
- Domain name of the home institution
- Affiliation, i.e. information on the status of the person concerned within their home institution and/or community AAI (student, staff, member, etc.)
- Assurance, i.e. information on the reliability of the information

Optional information

- Service/community-specific authorizations and group memberships
- Other identifiers such as ORCID
- Consent already given to Acceptable Use Policies and other terms of use or acknowledgement thereof

If a service requires additional information, the relevant attributes/claims can be documented in a service access policy. The template required for this is linked at <https://doc.nfdi-aa1.de/policies/>.

2.3 Authorization

There are different opportunities to realize the authorisation. You can use virtual organisations, resource capabilities, home-idp based authorisation and assurance-based authorisation

2.3.1 Virtual Organisation

In this authorisation type, services provide resources to Virtual Organisations. Membership is managed by the community itself, e.g. by VO administrators that add (or remove) users to their VO.

The VO membership is transmitted via entitlements claims and the group keyword (see [AARC-G069](#)). This and the already registered VOs are defined at the Community AAI instances. Users can be organised in hierarchical (tree-topology) groups (i.e. VOs and sub-VOs).

Example:

```
"urn:geant:dfn.de:nfdi.de:<consortium>:group:<vo-name>:<sub-vo>#login.antmaster.de",
```

2.3.2 Resource capabilities

Some services or Communities require an additional authorisation structure, that shifts the authorisation decision away from the service towards the Community-AAI. Then, the Community AAI makes specific statements about what a user may do, e.g. whether or not to start VMs, or which datasets may be accessed.

This information is also transmitted via the entitlements claim, but then using the res keyword (see [AARC-G027](#)).

Example:

```
"urn:geant:dfn.de:nfdi.de:<consortium>:res:ant-dataset-42:read#login.antmaster.de",  
"urn:geant:dfn.de:nfdi.de:<consortium>:res:start-vm#login.antmaster.de",
```

2.3.3 Home-IdP based authorisation

Enables authorisation based on attributes that are administered by a Home-IdP. This includes what kind of status or affiliation a person has (e.g. student) or whether specific access legitimization was given to a user. Attributes and values used in this case need to be agreed upon between Identity Providers and Services.

In addition, a Home-IdP may communicate entitlements such as VO membership or Resource capabilities. In order to prevent conflicting statements, this should be done in close collaboration between the administrators of Home-IdPs, Community-AAIs, VO Admins and Services.

2.3.4 Assurance based authorisation

Assurance describes the quality of an identity. This enables to differentiate between specific quality levels of an identity.

IdPs provide assurance information on the identity of the user, for example stating that a photo ID has been checked and/or that multi factor authentication is employed. This is expressed by the user's Home organisation and forwarded within the AAI. If the organisation provides only the assurance information but not the fulfilled profiles, the AAI adds the profile information.

The REFEDS Assurance Framework (RAF) defines individual assurance components that describe a users identity. This allows for differentiation between the quality of the ID-Vetting, the attribute freshness and the uniqueness of the identifiers used.

2.4 Policies

The [NFDI-AAI Policy Framework](#) addresses organizational, legal and technical aspects of the operation of Community AAIs and their superordinate infrastructure, concerning

- the management of Virtual Organizations (VOs)
 - Top Level Policy
 - VO Membership Management Policy (VOMMP)

- VO Lifecycle Policy
- attribute/claim profiles - Infrastructure Attribute Policy (IAP), see above, section 'Attributes'
- data protection - Policy on Processing of Personal Data (PPPD), mandatory for all participants and service operators, in addition to this
 - Templates for data protection notices and procedure directories
- security Incident Response Procedure (SIRP), mandatory for all participants and service operators
- acceptable Use Policies (AUPs)
 - Templates for VOs, CAAs and services

While the assignment of a service to one or more Community AAs generally does not require a separate decision-making process, there may be several Virtual Organizations (VOs) to choose from in the context of the Community AA(s). In particular, an assignment can be made based on the information from the relevant VO lifecycle policies and the associated AUPs. Service-specific features, such as special attributes/claims not covered by the IAP or special authorizations, can be documented in an optional Service Access Policy (SAP). If the higher-level AUPs are not considered sufficient, they can be supplemented with additional, service-specific conditions using a Service Acceptable Use Policy template. In any case, the provision of data protection information for the use of the respective service is mandatory. There are templates in German and English for this purpose.

2.4.1 Incident Response

Compliance with the [Security Incident Response Procedure \(SIRP\)](#) is mandatory for all participants in the NFDI-AAI. This policy document is based on the AARC guideline [AARC-1051 Guide to Federated Security Incident Response for Research Collaboration](#), which in turn further specifies the communication processes for security incidents defined in the [Security Incident Response Trust Framework for Federated Identity \(Sirtfi\)](#). In this respect, compliance with the Sirtfi framework must also be ensured for the relevant service and service operator. One of the most important points here is the provision of a security contact, ideally a functional email address, which must be entered in the SAML metadata of the relevant service provider (if available) and subscribed to the nfdi-aa-security@listserv.dfn.de mailing list.

2.5 Metadata management in the NFDI-AAI

In this context, the term metadata refers to the technical and organisational information provided in a standardised syntax that is necessary for IdPs and SPs to be able to communicate with each other.

Due to the different levels of the [NFDI-AAI architecture](#), metadata management takes place in different places:

2.5.1 Federations and Community AAs

Ideally, the edu-ID system is used as an interface between the home IdPs from eduGAIN/DFN-AAI and the community AAs. This is the only way to ensure that users

can be uniquely identified throughout their academic life and across the various community AAls.

In this respect, the service provider components of the Community-AAI proxies must be registered like normal service providers in the “edu-ID” federation. This is done via the administration interface of the DFN-AAI metadata administration. Details on edu-ID onboarding are documented at <https://doku.tid.dfn.de/de:aai:eduid:spconfig>.

2.5.2 Community AAls and associated services

See the relevant subsection of “Connection to the Community AAls”.

2.5.3 Community AAls and infrastructure proxy

The “NFDI” federation, which is also managed via the DFN-AAI metadata administration, exists to connect the identity provider components of the community AAI proxies and the service provider component of the infrastructure proxy. The URL of this NFDI federation metadata is: <https://www.aai.dfn.de/metadata/dfn-aai-nfdi-metadata.xml>

The certificate for signature validation of this metadata is the same as that provided for the DFN-AAI federation metadata, see <https://doku.tid.dfn.de/de:metadata>.

The attributes of the currently valid attribute profile (see above, Attributes) must be released for the SP component of the infrastructure proxy with the entity ID <https://infraproxy.nfdi-aai.dfn.de/idp/shibboleth>.

2.5.4 Infrastructure proxy and services to be connected to it

As mixed operation of SAML and OpenID Connect/OAuth2-capable services is expected here, the connection is currently (end of 2024) still direct and manual.

2.6 Comparison of connection as a community service vs. NFDI infrastructure service

2.6.1 Connection as a community service vs. NFDI infrastructure service:

Connection as a community service

- Advantages:
 - Simple connection to a community
 - Fast implementation
 - Flexibility in configuration
 - Chargeable
- Disadvantages
 - Dependence on the community
 - Any changes to the community interface can lead to problems
 - No guarantee for the availability and reliability of the community interface

Connection to an NFDI infrastructure service

- Advantages:
 - Standardized interface for all NFDI infrastructures
 - Guarantee for the availability and reliability of the interface
 - Simple scalability and maintenance
 - Cost-neutral
- Disadvantages:
 - More complex implementation
 - Dependence on the NFDI infrastructure
 - Any changes to the NFDI interface can lead to problems

2.6.2 Connection to one community vs. connection to several communities

When connecting a service to federated identity or authorisation infrastructures, the question arises as to whether a single community or several communities should be integrated. Both approaches have different requirements, advantages and challenges, which are compared below.

Connection to one community

Connecting to just one community is usually simple and straightforward. As only one interface needs to be integrated, the implementation can usually be realised quickly. This approach also allows a high degree of flexibility in configuration, as the requirements and framework conditions of the selected community can be specifically addressed. However, it should be noted that this approach can be costly - for example, due to licence costs or fees for support and integration.

Connection to multiple communities

In contrast, connecting to multiple communities involves a significantly more complex implementation. Different interfaces, protocols and authorisation concepts must be taken into account and coordinated. This also results in a dependency on several external partners, which can increase the maintenance effort. It can be particularly problematic if changes are made to the interfaces of individual communities - such adjustments must then be taken into account by the system. On the other hand, this approach is often cost-neutral as long as no commercial services or additional services are required.

3 Service integration

3.1 General procedure for service integration

The SAML2.0 or OpenID Connect (OIDC) protocols can be used to connect a service to the NFDI-AAI. All community AAIs and the NFDI infrastructure proxy support the connection via these two SSO protocols. Due to the architecture of the NFDI AAI, the community AAIs and the infrastructure proxy are each individual IdPs that hide the complexity of the federation world. It is therefore sufficient if a service to be connected

can configure exactly one IdP. The information to be stored in the service is provided by the respective IdP (one of the CAAls or the infrastructure proxy). For SAML, this is the IdP metadata in XML format and for OIDC it is the list of relevant endpoints and capabilities, as well as `client_id` and `client_secret`. On the other hand, the service must provide its own information, which can be stored in the IdP. This is XML metadata (SAML) or the `redirect_uri` (OIDC).

The exact technical implementation depends on the software or technology used. Many frameworks (e.g. CMS systems such as Typo3 or Wordpress) can be equipped with SAML or OIDC functionality via freely available plugins.

For generic web applications, the software Shibboleth SP (for SAML) or `mod_auth_openidc` (for OIDC) can be used, which is installed in the Apache web server and enables the protection of an application via SAML or OIDC. The DFN-AAI wiki, for example, provides instructions for configuring the Shibboleth SP:

<https://doku.tid.dfn.de/de:shibsp>

3.2 Connection to the NFDI infrastructure proxy

In addition to SAML-capable service providers and OIDC relying parties, OAuth2 clients can also be connected to the NFDI infrastructure proxy. There is no standardized interface for this. For this reason, the connection of services in the initial phase of the NFDI-AAI is initially carried out manually and interactively together with the service providers. As the current implementation of the infrastructure proxy is Shibboleth software, reference can be made here to the relevant documentation for [SAML](#) and [OIDC/OAuth2](#). Dynamic Client Registration is not supported until further notice for security reasons. In principle, the required technical details do not differ from those required for the connection to the community AAls - see below. Furthermore, the requirements of the policy framework must be observed (see above), in particular contact details, data protection information and, if applicable, own AUPs and a service access policy.

The aim is to exclusively support OpenID Connect (and possibly OAuth2) as the standard in future. This would make it possible to use [OpenID Federation](#) both for connecting services and for connecting to other infrastructures (especially EOSC). The restriction to one standard would also facilitate the development of a graphical service integration front end. A checklist for connecting services to the NFDI infrastructure is available here: <https://doc.nfdi-aa1.de/infraproxy/>

3.3 Connection to the community AAls

The following five steps are the basis for connecting a service to the central instance of a CAAI. Detailed instructions can be found in the [documentation](#).

1. registration with the CAAI
2. creation of a service endpoint
3. implementation of the CAAI interface
4. configuration of the CAAI settings
5. testing and validation

3.3.1 AcademicID

The connection to Academic ID as a community AAI can be requested at sso-support@gwdg.de.

Academic ID offers both OIDC and SAML connections. The following information is required:

- Name of the service
- Responsible contact persons (at least 2)
- Required attributes

The following is also required for OIDC:

- Redirect URL and Root URL

For SAML is additionally required:

- Metadata URL

Further information can be found here (WIP German translation):

https://docs.gwdg.de/doku.php?id=de:services:it_security:aa:serviceowner

3.3.2 didmos

didmos can be used by the specialist consortia in two ways: Either a client is created for the subject consortium in the multitenant didmos instance (see <https://portal.didmos.nfdi-aa:de>), which is operated free of charge for the subject consortia, or - if there is a need for subject consortia-specific extensions - such a subject consortium can have its own didmos instance set up and operated in order to be able to commission such extensions. didmos supports SAML and OIDC, as well as Dynamic Client Registration (but only in a separate instance by arrangement).

In both cases, it is first necessary to contact a technician via nfdi-support@daasi.de. All further steps will then be discussed.

The following information is required:

- Name of the service
- Responsible contact persons (at least 2)
- Required attributes
- For which consortium is the service intended?

For OIDC is additionally required:

- Redirect URI

For SAML is additionally required:

- Metadata (as URL or attached XML file)

3.3.3 Reg-APP

In principle, the connection to the test instance is established by initially contacting the advisors specified in the KIT service description by email. The service operators should provide the (redirect) URL of the service in the case of an OIDC connection and the XML metadata of the service provider in the case of a SAML connection, provided this data is available in advance. Everything else - such as the provision of OIDC credentials - will then also be clarified by email.

3.3.4 Unity

To connect a service to the test instance via OIDC, a client request must be made. This can easily be done at login-dev.helmholtz.de/oauthhome/. Click on “No account? Sign Up” and then on ‘Oauth2/OIDC-Client-Registration’.

Fill in the necessary information in the form, agree to the Acceptable Use Policy and click on “Submit”. The user name corresponds to the client ID and the password to the client secret.

As soon as the application has been checked by AAI administrators, they will get in touch with the specified service admin contacts to let them know whether the application has been accepted or whether any further questions need to be clarified.

To connect via SAML, please send an email to ds-support@fz-juelich.de with the following information:

- Name of the service
- Short description of the service
- URL to the privacy policy
- E-mail address(es) of the service admin contact(s)
- Email address(es) of the security contact(s) of the service
- Local security contact (your local certificate)
- Postal address of the organization providing the service
- Entity ID
- Return URL
- Logo of the service (link to a png file)

Further information on registering services can be found here. If you have any questions or problems, please send an e-mail to ds-support@fz-juelich.de.

4 Need Support with IAM4NFDI?

If you are still unsure or need further assistance, please don't hesitate to contact our team under aai-helpdesk@lists.nfdi.de.